

The High-Degree Gravity (g)-modes Sequences in HD 4539

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Abstract

We analysed one of the brightest pulsating subdwarf B star, HD 4539 (=EPIC 220641886). The star was observed by the Kepler Spacecraft K2 mission during Campaign 8. The full K2 data set spans ~ 80 days, and from this we extract 153 significant pulsation frequencies. K2 dataset had revealed that HD 4539 is a hybrid sdB pulsator giving it a rich asteroseismic potential. The amplitude spectrum of the star displays a rich content of gravity g - modes. The low-frequency region ($< 2000 \mu\text{Hz}$) includes at least 144 independent g - modes, while the high frequency region ($> 2000 \mu\text{Hz}$) consists of only 9 pressure p - modes. We used asymptotic period spacing to identify the modal degree of the majority of the modes, ranging from $l = 1$ to $l = 12$, apart from $l = 3$ and $l = 11$ modes, that are not seen. For the first time in a subdwarf B pulsator, the identification of the modes seems quite robust up to $l = 6$.

1 Introduction

Hot subluminescent stars of spectral type B (sdB) have been identified as core helium-burning stars. They are located between the Horizontal Branch (HB) and white dwarf cooling track, on a narrow path on the so-called the Extreme Horizontal Branch (EHB Heber, 2016). Their effective temperatures range from 20 000 to 40 000 K. Their masses are close to the core-helium-flash mass $0.47 M_{\odot}$ and radii between 0.15 and $0.35 R_{\odot}$, making them compact objects (Heber, 2016). These stars are basically He-burning cores surrounded by very thin hydrogen envelopes ($M_{env} < 0.01 M_{\odot}$). Such a small mass of the hydrogen envelope does not allow sdB stars to climb up the Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB). Therefore, after helium has been exhausted in their cores, sdB stars move directly towards the white dwarf cooling tracks. Given that the majority are found in binary systems (Maxted *et al.*, 2001; Copperwheat *et al.*, 2011) several binary interaction mechanisms are involved to explain the existence of sdB stars (in detail Han *et al.*, 2002; Paczynskii, 1976; Han *et al.*, 2000; Webbink, 1984). In order to complete the evolutionary picture of sdB, we need to compare the theoretical models with the actual observations. SdB stars are found to pulsate non-radially (Charpinet *et al.*, 1996, 1997; Kilkenny *et al.*, 1997) which provides us with an independent way to probe their interiors and test the theoretical models through asteroseismology. SdB pulsators are classified as V361 Hya stars and V1093 Her stars based on their periods. The V361 Hya stars (short-period pulsators) were found by Kilkenny *et al.* (1997) and their frequencies are higher than $2000 \mu\text{Hz}$ and their amplitudes are low, up to few millimagnitudes. These stars are dominated by pressure p-modes. The latter class is dominated by gravity g-modes, which are usually pulsating with frequencies below $1000 \mu\text{Hz}$. The V1093 Her stars were discovered in 2003 by Green *et al.* (2003). Some sdB pulsators show both kinds of modes, hence they are called hybrid pulsators (Baran *et al.*, 2005; Schuh *et al.*, 2006). The Kepler space mission (Borucki *et al.*, 2008) allowed us to analyse these stars to a greater extent. Thanks to the uninterrupted high quality space light-curves from Kepler and later K2, the seismic tools such as rotational multiplets and asymptotic period spacing are finally becoming useful for sdB stars as well.

HD 4539 is a well known, bright ($V = 10.24$ mag), sdB star for which g-mode pulsations have been suspected in 2007 by Schoenaers & Lynas-Gray (2007). The authors report the discovery of non-radial pulsations and it was discovered through spectroscopic data via line profile variations, however without mode identification. Schoenaers & Lynas-Gray (2008) tried to identify non-radial modes, which are described by spherical harmonics with radial order (n), modal degree (l), and azimuthal degree (m) by using synthetic moment method.

In our study we analyse full K2 light curve of HD 4539. Thanks to the continuous space-base observations covering more than 80 days, we have been able not only to confirm the pulsation in HD 4539 but also to identify pulsation modes. We make use of asymptotic period spacings and rotational multiplets in order to make inferences about the pulsation modes. HD 4539 is a challenging object for asteroseismological study given the quite complex patterns in its amplitude spectra. In order to check these patterns, firstly, we build sliding Fourier spectra of HD 4539. Then, we identify pulsation modes using only asymptotic period spacing. After identification of the modes, we construct échelle diagrams.

2 K2 observations

HD 4539 (=EPIC 220641886) is an sdB star with a Kepler magnitude of $K_p = 10.397$, RA = 11.87175, Dec = 9.9821377. The star was observed as part of the K2 Guest Observer program during Campaign 8 for 81 days from 2016 January 04 to 2016 March 23. We downloaded all available data from the “Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes” (MAST)¹. Then, we extracted fluxes using aperture photometry (Bachulski *et al.*, 2016). We have clipped the data at 4σ and de-correlated fluxes which are then converted to parts per thousand (ppt) Fig. 1.

2.1 Fourier Analysis

In order to identify pulsation frequencies of HD 4539, we used Fourier transform technique to calculate its amplitude

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Figure 1: The K2 light curve of HD 4539

Figure 2: Gravity (top panel) and pressure (bottom) mode regions of HD 4539. The blue horizontal solid line represents the threshold as explained in the text.

spectrum. Then using a non-linear least square method, we fitted peaks in the amplitude spectra of the form of $(A_i \sin(\omega_i t + \phi_i))$. The resulting amplitude spectrum is given in Fig. 2 covering gravity (top panel) and pressure (bottom panel) mode regions. The frequency resolution of the data set is $0.22 \mu\text{Hz}$ as defined by $\Delta f = 1.5/T$, where T is the time coverage of the data set. We have defined the threshold as 5.6σ (Zong *et al.*, 2016) which equals to 0.007ppt . We excluded all the frequencies below that level.

3 The Sliding Fourier Transform

The data set was then divided into small chunks of 2 days each. After performing the Fourier transform (FT) of each chunk, we produce the sliding FT by overlapping subsets Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Although K2 data set is significantly shorter than the Kepler nominal data set, we have looked at the stability of the oscillation modes in the K2 data of HD 4539 via the sliding Fourier Transform. We show three

different regions of frequencies. In the following plots (Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5) we see that both the pulsation frequencies and amplitudes of some modes show variations in time (vertical axes). This is most likely indicating rotational beating with a period well above 80 days.

Figure 3: The top panel shows amplitude spectra of the main pulsation frequency. The bottom panel represents Sliding FT of the the main pulsation frequency ($83.39 \mu\text{Hz}$) showing small amplitude variability. Frequency is on the x-axis and time on the y-axis with colour indicating the amplitude.

3.1 Rotational Multiplets

In the presence of stellar rotation, non-radial modes of degree l split into $2l + 1$ components differing in azimuthal (m) number. In the case of slow rotation, the frequency splitting can be derived from the following equation

$$\nu_{n,l,m} = \nu_{n,l,0} + \Delta\nu_{n,l,m} = \nu_{n,l,0} + m \frac{1 - C_{n,l}}{P_{\text{rot}}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{n,l,m}$ is a rotational splitting. P_{rot} is a star's rotation period and $C_{n,l}$ is the Ledoux constant Ledoux (1951). We searched for multiplets in the entire range of the amplitude spectra, however we did not find any of them. The absence of multiplets due to the frequency splitting suggests two things: that the star is either oriented pole-on or that it has a very long rotation period, that the 80 days long data set is unable to detect. The lack of rotational multiplets in the amplitude spectra in the K2 data set of HD 4539 casts a doubt on their conclusion of the (Schoenaers & Lynas-Gray, 2007) who claimed that the star is oriented almost edge-on with the inclination 85° . Both g - and p -mode regions display complex patterns due to either not long enough observing run or non-linear mode interactions which makes them elusive.

Figure 4: Same as in Fig. 3 but covering other set of g-mode frequencies.

Figure 5: Same as in Fig. 4 but covering lower amplitude g-mode frequencies.

3.2 Asymptotic Period Spacing

In order to identify the pulsation modes in the g-mode region, we used asymptotic period spacing. In the asymp-

totic limit ($n \gg l$), consecutive radial overtones are evenly spaced in period (Charpinet *et al.*, 2000). For given n and l values, periods of consecutive overtones can be derived from the following equation,

$$\Pi_{l,n} = \frac{\Pi_0}{\sqrt{l(l+1)}}n + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where $\Pi_{l,n}$ is the period spacing, Π_0 and ϵ are constants, (Reed *et al.*, 2011). It has been determined that the dipole ($l=1$) period spacing for sdB stars is ~ 250 s (Reed *et al.*, 2011). For HD 4539 the average of the period spacing for the dipole modes is $\Pi_{l=1} = 256.5$ s. Using the ratio between the modes we searched for the potential sequences in the period domain. We have found 10 sequences between $l=1$ and $l=12$, excluding $l=3$ and $l=11$ which are not seen, likely due to cancellation effects. Since the period spacing changes with l (gets lower with increasing l), the identification of the modes seems quite robust, at least up to $l=6$.

3.3 Échelle Diagrams

We have produced the échelle diagrams for $1 \leq l \leq 12$ and all diagrams show deviations from the period modulo (average period spacing). In Fig. 6 we have shown an example of the échelle diagrams for high degree modes of $l=5$ and $l=6$ respectively.

4 Conclusion

We have analysed K2 observations of one of the brightest known sdBs, confirming that HD 4539 is a V1093 Her-type pulsator, and identifying more than 150 pulsation frequencies majority of which are g-modes 144 and only 9 are p-modes. Our goal was to identify modes for future asteroseismic modeling. We could not use rotational multiplets to assign both modal degree and radial order since no rotational multiplets were detected. Using asymptotic relations, however, we have identified sequences of near-consecutive modes for degrees ($1 \leq l \leq 12$) which will be crucial to make a realistic asteroseismic models of the star. The modes can be seen also in the échelle diagrams with their characteristic shapes, which might be inferred trapped modes (Østensen *et al.*, 2014; Uzundag *et al.*, 2017).

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Figure 6: Échelle diagram of HD 4539 for $l=5$ (top panel, blue dots), and $l=6$ (bottom panel, orange dots), the rest of the dots are distributed randomly in certain average value.

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